

Towards a phylo-k-mer meta-index and classifier for phylogenetic placements in a collection of trees

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Abstract

We previously developed the idea of phylo-k-mers, an original approach in which either nucleotide or amino acid k-mers are computed from a sequence model [1]. More precisely, using a Maximum-Likelihood phylogenetic model of ancestral reconstruction, we compute a matrix of posterior probabilities for each sequence position and tree branch. Then, using this matrix, we compute a k-mer and its associated probability of belonging to a tree branch (a phylo-k-mer). These k-mers are then indexed, using the assumption that they "might" be sampled in the future. As such, phylo-k-mers belong to a category of probabilistic (predicted, not "observed") k-mer methods. This should not be confused with methods such as Bloom filters, where only "observed" k-mers are indexed and queried via probabilistic techniques. In practice, we introduce a probability threshold to explore a reasonable fraction of the phylo-k-mer space.

Phylo-k-mer applications can also be seen as a classification problem. K-mers from sampled sequences are compared to the phylo-k-mer index, and tree branches maximizing the accumulation of high probabilities are selected as the class. This should not be confused with classification into a taxonomy (e.g., Kraken-like approaches [2]). First, in our approach, selecting an internal tree branch means that it was the most likely divergence point: all branches in the subtree showed lower probabilities. On the other hand, Kraken-like approaches fall back to a last common ancestor because no precise position in the subtree could be selected with enough confidence. Second, our method provides an estimate of classification uncertainty. These points are essential when high-precision classification of environmental sequences (e.g., metabarcoding or metagenomics) is targeted. For instance, in viral emergence surveillance, large fractions of sampled sequences may originate from non-referenced genomes, but precise evaluation of divergence and uncertainty is essential for diagnostics.

Previously, we applied phylo-k-mer-based classification to the problems of phylogenetic placement [3] and viral genome recombination detection [4]. In both cases, we built alignment-free methods with a sensitivity comparable to alignment-based methods but with up to two orders of magnitude speed-up. However, the approach also showed several limitations. In particular, when analyzing raw metagenomes,

some reads from untargeted clades can randomly match phylo-k-mers of high probability. Simultaneously, reads from targeted but divergent clades can match many phylo-k-mers of low probability. This results in the introduction of false positives, e.g., classification of sequences unrelated to the index but associated with a score similar to true positives. A workaround is to filter edge cases with fast local alignment, but this reduces the advantages of using our alignment-free approach.

Here, we extended our phylo-k-mer classifier to simultaneously take into account the probability and the collinearity of phylo-k-mer matches as a means to filter sequences that are actually related to a particular phylo-k-mer index. We implemented a simple scoring scheme based on entropy and accumulated probabilities. In practice, we rapidly extended this idea to allow classification into a collection of phylogenies. First, we build a phylo-k-mer index for each phylogeny. Then, we build a meta-index of phylo-k-mers selected among these indices. A similar classifier is then used to evaluate which index should be selected, then classification into the corresponding tree branches can be computed (Figure 1). This approach appears to be sufficient even when phylogenies are based on homologous sequences. For instance, it can successfully distinguish gene trees showing similar domains.

We will present in detail the method developed and introduce preliminary results related to the classification of protein sequences into a collection of gene families. We also aim to discuss several aspects that still call for improvement. For instance, we identified some computational bottlenecks in the current algorithm and tried to develop a pseudo-entropy score to reduce cache misses.

Figure 1. To classify a sequence into a collection of phylogenies, our meta-classifier aims to distinguish the correct phylo-k-mer index (green) from the thousands of other index (red banana). Using a phylo-k-mer meta-index, position and probability associated to k-mer matches are used to compute an entropy (Y-axis) and a probabilistic score (X-axis). This combination allows to select the index to load for precise classification in the selected phylogeny.

References

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